

SCIENTIFIC AND THEORETICAL BASIS OF THE CONCEPT OF PRODUCTION IN MODERN TELEVISION

Malika Islamova

Uzbekistan National University PhD

E-mail: malika.daniyeva@gmail.com

Phone: +998 99 816 03 30

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10351609>

In this article, the idea, to trace the formation, development and distribution of producer functions on TV in terms of the formation of new professional competencies of a television journalist. In accordance with the stated goal, the following tasks are set: - to define the concept of television producing;

В этой статье идея, проследить становление, развитие и распределение функций продюсера на ТВ в аспекте формирования новых профессиональных компетенций телевизионного журналиста. В соответствии с обозначенной целью ставятся следующие задачи: - дать определение понятию телевизионное продюсирование;

Ключевые слова: продюсер, телевизионное продюсирование, телевидение, развитие, события.

Annotatsiya

Mazkur maqolada telejurnalstning yangi kasbiy malakalarini shakllantirish nuqtai nazaridan televideniya prodyuserlik funksiyalarining shakllanishi, rivojlanishi va tarqalishini kuzatishdan iborat. Belgilangan maqsadga muvofiq quyidagi vazifa qo'yiladi: - televideniya ishlab chiqarish tushunchasini aniqlash.

Kalit so'zlari: televidenie, so'z, musiqa, intershum, kino, televideniye, siymolar, ekran, san'at, tasvirlar, ishlab chiqarish, voqealar.

Introduction. Modern television remains one of the most accessible mass media. At the same time, it performs a number of important social functions that affect the most important social processes. Media is everywhere, even if we don't realize it. A television producer is, in fact, an organizer of television production, who is primarily a co-author of a reporter. The main task of a television producer is to help a journalist gather material within a limited time. His position can be called differently, for example, in Europe and America, this responsibility is taken by line and executive producers, about whose work we will talk in more detail below.

To indicate a certain vector of our research, we define the term "producer" - (English produce - production) - producer, program organizer, representative of the television company, studio, editor. Performs artistic and organizational-financial control over the creation of a television work, is responsible for compliance with the contracts concluded with the company, studio, and editors regarding the compliance of the created television program with their requirements and contract terms.

To the topic about books analysis (Literature review). The theoretical framework is based on the works of domestic and foreign researchers, i.e Kadyrov M. " Avesta " and watch arts " you can find information based on the history of television production. Scientific articles by I.N. Kemarskaya, S.A. Muratova, D. Gubina, K. Kellison, O.F Maidurova, S.N. Ilchenko

and other authors who studied the theory and practice of television production describe their practical perspectives on the development of television production today.

Research methodology (Research Methodology). Scientific in research tracking , documents learning and conversation methods used . In our country state and non-state TV channels in the activity of the producer participation observation method through was studied . With that together present in the day leader television producers with exactly this in the subject conversations take went _ In particular series social and entertainment projects producer " Sevimli TV" producer and present in the day to his media group have Baxtiyor Safarov modern of the profession development stages and own in the activity achievement and disadvantages about details information gave .

Another one TV producer , chief producer of " Renaissance TV". Parviz Fattoyev with conversation in the process to television young passionate creative approach have producers the missing one and this of the field theoretical part too fast in pictures to develop importance to give that it is necessary separately stopped. Because now in a narrow range expert of being himself scarcity does because TV project creator one of time both creative and technical in itself bias knowledge and to the skill have to be of TV projects lucky at the exit important role is playing

Analysis and results (Analysis and results). In fact TV producer modern occupation considered his why are you long to the past go to wear our scientists justified respectively is being proved . Professor M. Kadirov According to his opinion , the Mughals wrote " Avesto " odes and narratives and prayers execution doer qualified people are " fireplaces next to such of the Mughals gangs decision found , they between known level specialization happened giving , word masters , reciters , hafiz , players separately into categories those who are divided ¹. Or , ancient in cities people numbers and holidays public watch in the style of be past For example , XX century At the beginning of Bukhara in the emirate art works with Jalal mirzaboshi with Mirza Abdurahim said people were engaged in. To art Ashufite was _ of our people public games and performances essentially to each other connected the only one artistic activity product is counted . Because this cultural events theatrical watch of art to himself special forms in them performer , viewer , natural the scene is a park and field yes , that's it with together , tnuayyan vital scenario , popular directing and natural There is also a decoration . Such national games and performances his own execution to be done according to alone and public (group) view demonstration to be done can. For example , single performers - bakovuls , curious , bakhshis , muqallids , bear , monkey and snake players , word _ masters , poets their own creative the product alone without execution they will It's creative performers alone without city and village in their neighborhoods sharing , people _ accumulative crowded places - market , guzar , neighborhood and big open in the fields own the arts demonstration have reached Certain to groups united without creative activity with engaged in artists - singers , musicians , entertainers , clowns , porters , stone lifters wrestlers , wrestlers and another that's it such as art type with busy has been performers while own

¹ Kadyrov M. " Avesta " and watch arts // " Avesta " and his humanity in development Is it dead ? - Tashkent- Urganch , 2001. - B.44. 4 B. Saifullayev . Watch art history and theory . - T. , 2014, p. 55.

skills basically big in parks , market in squares , theaters , and theaters watch to show intended special in scenes demonstration have ²reached

Summary and suggestions (Conclusion/Recommendations).

Our time occupations and to them has been need more and more increased is going Of these directions inside television production job in our country practical in terms of developing from professions is one But this of the profession theoretical basics full not formed . This is a professional expert personnel in preparation one series difficulties cause is releasing . Shortcomings eliminate reach and scientific theoretical base in creating abroad from experience use to the goal according to will be because television production many abroad in universities specialty science as is being taught . We have while experience now Demand is increasing .

² B. Saifullayev . Watch art history and theory . - T. _ , 2014.

References:

- 1.Uzbekistan Republic of Constitution. -T.: Uzbekistan , 2014 .
 - 2.Mirziyoev Sh.M. Critical analysis, strict discipline and personal responsibility should be the daily rule of every leader's activity. - T.: Uzbekistan, 2017.
 - 3.Mirziyoev Sh.M. _ Together we will build a free and prosperous, democratic country of Uzbekistan. Speech at the joint meeting of the chambers of the Oliy Majlis dedicated to the inauguration ceremony of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Tashkent, 2016. p. 56.
 - 4.Mirziyoev Sh.M. Critical analysis, strict discipline and personal responsibility should be the daily rule of activity of every leader. Report at the extended meeting of the Cabinet of Ministers dedicated to the main results of the socio-economic development of our country in 2016 and the most important priorities of the economic program for 2017, January 14, 2017 - Tashkent, Uzbekistan, 2017. 104- b.
 - 5.Mirziyoev Sh.M. Ensuring the rule of law and human interests is the guarantee of the country's development and people's well-being. Speech at the solemn ceremony dedicated to the 24th anniversary of the adoption of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan. December 7, 2016- Tashkent, Uzbekistan, 2017. p. 48.
 - 6.Akbarov HI Film Arts history. Own M U. 2005.
 - 7.Akbarov HI Film teledramaturgy: theory and practice. T.: Knowledge. 200 5.
 - 8.Akbarov HI In the world of cinema and television. - T.: G'. Ghulam. Publishing House of Literature and Art, 2003.
 - 9.Aliev M. Fundamentals of cinema. - T.: Teacher, 1993.
 - 10.Khidoyatokhjaev T. Cinema and video equipment. T.: Uzbekistan, 1990.
 - 11.ZM Babur. Boburnama. - T.: Teacher, 1994
 - 12.Nesterenko FP and the team of authors. Dictionary. Journalism, advertising, public relations. - T.: Zar Kalam, 2003.
 - 13.Ethical criteria in the creation of television and radio programs: "INTERNEWS", 1998.
 - 14.Critical theories of mass media : yesterday and today. Paul A. Taylor and John Lee Harris (trans.). Open University Press. 2008.
 - 15.Critical theories of mass media. Then and now. Open University Press . 2008.
 - 16.PuteshesTelevideniyeie pisatelya. Christopher Vogler. 000. Alpina non-fiction. Moscow. 2015
 - 17.Akbarov HI "Film teleregissura montage". Tashkent. "Ilm-Ziya" 2007 year
 - 18.Yu. Lotman. Semiotics of cinema and problems of cinematography. [http||royallib.ru|book](http://royallib.ru/book)
 - 19.Akbarov HI Cinema and television: creative educational process. T.: Music, 2012.
 - 20.M. Aliev. Film works. - T.: Uzbekistan, 1993.
 - 21.Akbarov H. In the world of television and cinema. T.: Publishing House of Literature and Art named after G'. Ghulam. 1993.
 - 22.Prokorov EP Vvedenie v teoriyu journalistiki. M.: Aspect-Press 2002.
 - 23.Kinotelecommunication: nature and content. Myself . 2008-2010 parts 1-5.
- 1.[www. ziyonet.uz](http://www.ziyonet.uz) - educational information network of Uzbekistan.
 - 2.[www. media.utmn.ru](http://www.media.utmn.ru).
 - 3.[www/ uzbekkino.uz](http://www/uzbekkino.uz).
 - 4.www/ziyonet.uz